

Research on the "1+1+N" Innovation Model to Help Build Urban Greenways from the Perspective of Transforming Major Social Contradictions - A Case Study of Jinjiang District, Chengdu

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Abstract: As a product in the era of urbanization, greenway has the essential functional attribute of solving urban development. With the continuous innovation of greenway construction forms, the concept of multiple integrated development will become a new mode of greenway construction. Based on this, taking the greenway construction in Jinjiang District of Chengdu as the research object, starting from "the main contradiction in society has been transformed into the contradiction between growing needs for a better life", the paper analyzes it from the perspectives of culture, tourism, sports and public welfare, aiming to explore the innovation of urban greenway development mode with people's better life as the core. In order to provide reference for other urban greenway construction.

Keywords: Urban greenway, "1+1+N" innovation model, Integrated development.

INTRODUCTION

The report to the 19th National Congress pointed out that as socialism with Chinese characteristics has entered a new era, the principal contradiction facing society has changed to that between unbalanced and inadequate development and the people's ever-growing needs for a better life. With the improvement of people's living standards and the diversification of consumer demand, people are also increasingly favoring the consumption mode that integrates online and offline. Greenway is a linear space carrier with multiple functions such as ecology, society, culture and landscape, which can integrate and develop with "sports, tourism, business and agriculture" to create new vitality.

Taking Jinjiang District of Chengdu as an example, this paper, starting from the structure and characteristics of the greenway mode, analyzes the basic theory needed to build the "1+1+N" innovative greenway mode, analyzes the current situation of greenway construction in Jinjiang District of Chengdu, and deeply studies its existing problems, so as to

further promote the development of global tourism and characteristic culture, and actively integrate and innovate with agriculture, culture, sports, research, public welfare and cultural innovation. Finally, the construction of "1+1+N" innovative greenway mode is conducive to the organic integration of local cultural industry and greenway, and lays a solid foundation for promoting local economic development and industrial innovation.

1. Requirements of The Times for the construction of urban greenway

Urban development and renewal are changing dynamically, and people's yearning for a better life and their demand for happiness are also constantly rising.^[1] In recent years, urban greenways have become a closely related part of people's lives, as they can walk, jog, cycle and even take photos. Greenway is one of the important means to protect and strengthen the natural landscape. In the case of the shortage of animals in our country, increasing the construction of urban greenway can provide habitat for other organisms and achieve

urban species diversity. Not only that, the emergence of a new sports space such as greenway can drive the development of many sports industries in China, such as urban marathon, cycling, jogging, fitness running and other events, help promote national fitness and create a new scene of sports consumption. Finally, urban greenway can effectively relieve the pressure of urban traffic. With the increase of urban population, traffic congestion has become a major problem hindering urban development. The construction of urban greenway can provide residents with a choice of green travel, reduce motor travel, not only reduce traffic congestion, but also reduce air pollution caused by emissions, improve the ecological environment, thus promoting the development of related industries and building the image of Chengdu city. To realize the concept of urban ecological civilization construction of city green and common prosperity.

2. Analysis of current situation and problems of greenway in Jinjiang District of Chengdu

2.1. Status quo of greenway in Jinjiang District

(1) The situation of capital construction. In the context of fully practicing the concept of green development, Chengdu has proposed "all-area green enhancement" and built a five-level urban greening system of "ecological zone, greenway, park, small garden and micro-green space". In the process of construction, the regional cultural characteristics are highlighted, the construction theme of one park, one theme and one place, the typical cultural symbols of Jinjiang are refined, and the elements such as sculpture, landscape wall and intangible cultural heritage are incorporated into the construction of the small garden to enhance the cultural atmosphere. The whole area is planned to have 1,920 km of regional level greenway, 5,380 km of urban level greenway and 9,630 km of community level greenway. The construction of district-level greenways, including the Jinjiang Avenue greenway and the water system greenway, has been basically completed. Ten river channels have been built in the water system greenway, and the district has built a network of 280 kilometers of greenways.

(2) Development stage. At present, Chengdu Jinjiang Greenway is in the 1.0-2.0 stage of greenway. The 1.0 stage mode of greenway is the concept of "Greenway +", which extends the industrial chain of greenway well through the upgrading of industries and products of greenway. This kind of linear space, post station and some supporting facilities of the greenway itself need to be further constructed and operated to develop into a line of fine products in the future. The 2.0 stage mode of greenway is "+ greenway", which is the extension of industries, such as sports + greenway, culture + greenway, agriculture +

greenway, festival + greenway, etc. Greenway has become a fusion body, integrating local industries with characteristics.

2.2. Problem analysis of greenway mode in Jinjiang District of Chengdu

(1) There is a lack of supporting transportation facilities on both sides of Jinjiang River, and the green slow traffic system is not coherent. The water level of Jinjiang River is low all the year round, the slope ratio is large, and the design elevation of most Bridges along the river is low, resulting in the inability of large ships to navigate. The riverfront traffic system needs to be optimized. As Funan River is more prominent in the regulation process, the peripheral motor traffic lacks a unified channel to clear, and the transit traffic has a great impact on the arrival traffic on both sides of the Jinjiang River. In addition, the planned railway stations around the city have not yet been fully formed, and the proportion of motor vehicle travel within the Jinjiang City section continues to increase, resulting in greater traffic pressure around the river. The slow traffic is divided and discontinuous by motor lanes, and the slow traffic space in some sections of the river is even compressed by motor lanes. The lack of parking facilities in the periphery of Jinjiang leads to the lack of effective connection between fast and slow traffic.

(2) There are few public service facilities for cultural tourism on both sides of Jinjiang River, and the industrial support and driving capacity are not enough. The proportion of public facilities land is low, and the proportion of public facilities, housing and park green space in Jinjiang urban section is about 20:70:10, while the proportion of residential land is high. The number of public facilities is too small, and there is a lack of well-known and influential large scale brand festival activities. In addition to the cultural tourism industry, the industrial forms along the Jinjiang River are chaotic, and no independent business circle has been formed, and the existing business circle such as Chunxi Road, Taikuli and Lotus Pond is not well connected.

(3) The appearance of the cities on both sides of the Jinjiang River is old, and the vitality of the street communities is insufficient. Along the Jinjiang River, especially the area surrounded by the two rivers are mostly old and old urban areas, and the situation of "a thousand cities and a thousand houses" on both sides is obvious. The waterfront architectural style has no characteristics, the urban function is imperfect, the wall along the street is closed, the night scene is not bright enough, there is no festival and time mode, there is no landscape lighting function, and it can not create an atmosphere for the night economic development; Street community vitality is not high, the block openness, access rate is insufficient, the riverbank and adjacent sub-streets are not connected, waterfront space and community space integration is insufficient.

3. Construction of urban greenway "1+1+N" innovation model

The "1+1+N" innovation mode of urban greenway is mainly to integrate the greenway with local characteristics and culture, and integrate and innovate with industries such as agriculture, culture, sports, research, public welfare and cultural innovation. In the city, greenway can create a green space that can attract the participation of citizens, introduce urban life into the greenway, and create conditions for stimulating more urban renewal. Create small Spaces along the greenway that can accommodate art, sports, teaching and even charity activities, so that the public can participate and constantly reshape the environment here. [4]

Government departments and major shops can collect the people's demand for the expansion of the Greenway by issuing questionnaires. In combination with the local folk culture of Chengdu, they can set up commercial kiosks and characteristic cultural B&Bs along the loop of the Greenway and its surroundings, so as to make the Greenway more diversified and meet the needs of the masses. Citizens and tourists can irregularly put forward the shortcomings of greenway construction and improvement measures to relevant departments through wechat public account, municipal official website and other platforms, so as to strengthen the practicability of the greenway. The urban greenway "1+1+N" innovation model is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 "1+1+N" innovation mode of urban greenway

3.1. Objectives of the "1+1+N" innovation mode of urban greenway

For travel users, the main goal of the urban greenway "1+1+N" innovation model is to provide a multi-functional platform for the public to meet individual needs; For the characteristic agricultural products and cultural and creative products that can be sold, the goal is to provide merchants with publicity and transactions with users, strengthen the contact between user

s and merchants, users and users, and promote the development of product diversification.

3.2. Features of the "1+1+N" innovation model of urban greenway

(1) Multiple integration. The concept of "1+1+N" not only emphasizes the construction of the greenway itself, but also pays attention to the organic combination of local culture and industry with the greenway to form a diversified and integrated urban

n greenway. Gradually standardize and improve the concept, connotation and construction subjects of the greenway, and clarify the planning concept of "access, participation, perception, reading, appreciation and consumption" of the greenway. It fully embodies the idea of ecological civilization, deeply conforms to the requirements of The Times of the "two mountains" theory, and promotes the improvement of urban function quality and the transformation of development mode.

(2) Industrial upgrading. By combining greenway with local industries, industrial upgrading and innovation can be achieved, and local economic development and industrial fission can be promoted. Through planning the greenway framework system of "one axis, three rings, two mountains and seven belts", a market-oriented and commercial logic operation model is built, emphasizing the deep integration of agriculture, commerce, culture and tourism to promote value transformation.

(3) Innovative experience. The implementation of the greenway "1+1+N" concept can provide a richer and more diverse urban experience, both the natural scenery and leisure and entertainment functions of the greenway, and the display and experience of local culture and industry. In the future, a refined, intelligent and data-driven smart greenway platform will be built to esco

rt the green, low carbon and healthy development of the city, and add luster to the happiness and sense of gain of residents, and show the charm of the city.

CONCLUSIONS

Taking the greenway of Jinjiang District of Chengdu as an example, this paper systematically explores the greenway planning and construction mode of urban green integration from three aspects, such as extending function connotation, promoting function compound and constructing composite technical standard system, which has certain theoretical value and practical significance. ^[4]With the continuous advancement of urbanization, the connotation and extension of greenway will continue to be enriched, and the ideas and methods of greenway planning and construction need to be further studied and practiced. In particular, the quantitative evaluation of greenway value, the post-use evaluation of greenway, and the management and operation mode of greenway will become new research hotspots. At the same time, a composite technical standard system matching the composite function of the greenway should be built to ensure the landing and management of the greenway function.

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